

THE ESSENCE OF ECONOMIC IDEAS IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVOI

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about Alisher Navoi's views on economic issues in his works and the essence of the economic work he did in his career.

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Great thinker Alisher Navoi also has economic ideas in his works occupies an important place. His works and activities are especially commercial, trade issues are covered more thoroughly. In the works of A. Navoi mercantile work is favored, but extortionist and speculator are harsh criticized. As a statesman, A. Navoi made a great contribution to keeping the country peaceful and beautified. During his lifetime, he promised to build a thousand buildings, and he fulfilled his promise. He highly valued the place of work in man and society, and friendship. Alisher Navoi became famous as a poet and the leading minister of the state. These qualities of Navoi are clearly visible in his socio-economic and philosophical views. Navoi, as a progressive person of his time, has a humanistic and patriotic ideology jumped out of the frame. In order to improve the political and economic situation of his time, to improve the economic power of the country, he inculcated humanistic patriotism in people. he realized early that he needed to wake up.[1]

The work in which Navoi's early socio-economic thoughts were formed is Husayn in 1469 "Hiloliya" is a work dedicated to Boykara's accession to the throne. Hossein Boykara's accession to the throne was illuminated by Navoi's darkness "crescent", which equates to a three-day moon. He believed in strengthening the country's economic and political power, improving the social and material condition of the population, ending feudal wars, and establishing peace in the country. Navoi Husayn praises Boykara as the king of kings. But Navoi, along with praise, also puts forward important socio-economic ideas. Praising the ruler was a tactical method used by Navoi. Its main strategic goal was to improve the economic and political situation of the country, to establish a single center, a centralized, powerful state. Since the accession of Navoi Husayn Boykara to the throne, the country has been high in the socio-economic, socio-

political and cultural-educational spheres. He hopes that changes will be made.[2]

Paying great attention to the role of Navoi in the history of the country the economic situation depends on the intelligence and ability of the ruler of this country considers it related. If the ruler of the country, the sciences, especially if he perfectly knows economics, history, philosophy and political science, he He says that the country he is leading will be prosperous and rich, if the opposite happens, the country will be poor and ruined. Navoi left a name in history as a realist, saying that just as there is no body without a head, there is no state without a king. During the reign of Husayn Boygaro, relative development was noticeable in the country. Trade expanded, handicrafts and agriculture were well established. The construction of irrigation facilities also expanded. According to Navoi, the expansion of irrigation facilities for the conditions of Central Asia is one of the important factors leading to economic development. More than 70 under the direct leadership of A. Navoi canals and ditches were dug.[3]

The main part of the national income is rural was the income from the crops grown on the farm. Expanding the construction of irrigation facilities in the feudal society had a great impact on the development of the economy of that time. Navoi paid great attention to the expansion of the land, which was the main means of production during the period of feudalism, to increase its productivity (V. Zakhidov. Mir ideia i obraz A. Navoi). Navoi says that wealth can be found in two ways. First The way is to accumulate wealth by saving money with one's own labor, to accumulate and to live to one's self. Navoi was pleased to collect such wealth. He calls to divide the acquired and accumulated wealth into three parts, the first part for expenses, the second part for his and his family's needs, and the third part for the social benefits of the population. For example, in the work "Waqfiya" written in 1482, A. Navoi personally took the example of the income from his land and called to take a sufficient part of the income for his own expenses and family members, and spend the rest on the useful work of the population. Navoi strongly opposes the second way of getting wealth, that is, gaining wealth through theft, greed and coercion. He hates such things and describes people who gain wealth in this way as a parasitic class who live and gain wealth at the expense of society. One of the masterpieces of A. Navoi's work was written in 1500 "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" is a work. Navoi's economic thoughts in this work incarnate. In this work, Navoi divides society into social classes and tries to show their place in society. In the first part of the work to their classes and professions gives a characteristic. In the second and

third parts, good verbs and information about bad qualities is given. According to Navoi, Farmers, artisans and merchants with foreign relations play an important role in the production and creation of material wealth in the society and in increasing the wealth of the country. A. Navoi expresses the following thoughts about the farmer and his role in production: "The farmer who scatters grain is the one who opens the way of sustenance by plowing the land." The farmer, that is, the labor force, should and must be combined with the means of production. Navoi acknowledges the role of means of production in the creation of material wealth as follows: "The pair are two great wrestlers, they walk in front of them obeying their burden, they work together and step in step, the farmer is the same person in pushing them. World prosperity is the same. from them. Whatever they do, they will have enough food and blessings for the people!" So, the labor force of the peasant, his sheep and oxen are the tools of production, and the land is the object of labor, all of them together constitute the forces of production. Navoi work the decisive factor, the decisive element in production is the farmer, i.e expresses the opinion that it is the labor force. As mentioned above, According to A. Navoi, a single person cannot produce anything. In order to produce something, people of different categories must always be in direct contact with each other.[4]

For example, if a farmer needs work tools, a craftsman bread is needed, handicrafts and artisanal products are as necessary for farmers and herders as for water and air. Thus, just as a fish cannot live without water, all kinds of productive forces cannot develop without each other, says Navoi. In order to produce, farmers and other workers must interact with other producers in the process of production, distribution, exchange, and consumption. A. Navoi is a peasant in feudal society the importance of labor and the existing society of farmers admits that it was built on his work. A baker, a baker, a reaper, a farmer, and others look forward to the fruits of a farmer's labor. At the same time, the farmer is in tune with them and their work. Without them, nothing can be produced. So, with this, Navoi recognizes the relations of production. In his opinion, the farmer produces more of the products necessary for his needs with his work, and provides the society and its part that does not participate in production with material benefits. This opinion of Navoi corresponds to the opinion of physiocrats that by-product is only in agriculture. Navoi puts forward the very progressive idea that the development of agriculture is of great importance in increasing the power of the country. This idea was not only a very correct idea at that time, that is, the era of feudalism, which flourished, and its basis was agricultural production, but also a historical fact. A. Merchants, who

are an important class in Navoi society also divided into two groups. The first group is foreign trade relations group of leading merchants. The second group is the group of domestic sellers. Navoi looks positively at the merchants who trade with foreign countries and expresses sympathy for their activities. He looks critically at the traders in the markets, that is, the sellers. They serve their own interests and get rich at the expense of others. That's why their presence is a loss for the country, he says. The main goal of a trader is to make a profit. At the beginning of one hundred, there is a lot of trade, and there is a lot of desire in the heart of the second one. Here, the merchant is the opposite of the woodcutter in Navoi's "Hotam Toyi". The old man collects firewood and takes it to the market and sells it for money. He buys products, i.e. consumer products, for firewood money. This is where the "goods - money - goods" process takes place. The goal of the woodcutter's exchange is consumption value.

According to Navoi, the goal of a trader to buy is to sell at a higher price. A merchant wants to make one hundred and one thousand, says. He wants the little money he left to come back in large quantities, that is, him the object of exchange is value, or "money - commodity - money" (P-T-P). So, one of the first forms of capital existed in Navoi's opinion. He says the following about city merchants: "City merchants are treacherous, they seek profit for themselves and others, their profit is harm to the people, their dream is to buy cheap and sell expensive. When buying, they say cheap silk, when selling, they praise silk. If he can exchange the goods, there is no stopping him. His store has all the goods except honesty!" (A. Navoi. Collection of works. Volume XII, page 199). Although A.Navoi himself is not engaged in production and the production sector, with his intellectual and creative work he honors the classes necessary for the society, scientists, doctors, poets, engineers and others are necessary for the society. layer, he calls on the owners of this profession to realize their responsibilities and duties. His Holiness Alisher Navoi has repeatedly mentioned in his works that the development of the economy is compatible with the perfection of human spirituality. In particular, he connected the prosperity of the country and the people's well-being with high spirituality as follows: Until the threshing floor of lust and passion does not die, until the castle of passion does not die, until the soul of oppression does not die, the country does not die happily. Prosperous immortal.

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